

Supplementary Table 1: Participant characteristics

Characteristics	HoloLens 2 (n=11)	Magic Leap 2 (n=10)	Statistic
Age (years)	63 ± 8.6 [51-74]	69 ± 8.3 [53-82]	$t(19)=-1.759, p=0.095$
Sex, M/F	7/4	8/2	$X^2(1)=0.687, p=0.407$
Time since diagnosis (years)	6.3 ± 5.7 [1-20]	8.6 ± 3.8 [4-15]	$U=34.500, p=0.157$
Modified Hoehn & Yahr stage, 2/2.5	7/4	6/4	$X^2(1)=0.029, p=0.864$
MoCA score	26.2 ± 3.4 [18-29]	28.1 ± 2.2 [23-30]	$U=30.000, p=0.080$
LEDD (max. mg/day)	844.9 ± 673.8 [125-2400]	939.9 ± 488.2 [375-1738]	$t(19)=-0.367, p=0.718$
FoG, yes/no*	4/7	7/3	$X^2(1)=2.376, p=0.123$
MDS-UPDRS part III score	30.5 ± 13.8 [13-61]	31.6 ± 8.2 [21-46]	$t(19)=-0.210, p=0.836$
Fall history (number of falls in the past year)	3.1 ± 3.5 [0-10]	2.2 ± 3.4 [0-10]	$U=66.500, p=0.424$

Data are mean ± SD [range] unless indicated otherwise. M = male, F = female, MoCA = Montreal Cognitive Assessment, LEDD = Levodopa Equivalent Daily Dose, FoG = Freezing of gait, MDS-UPDRS = MDS-Unified Parkinson's disease rating scale. *The presence of FoG is defined by a non-zero score on the New Freezing of Gait Questionnaire.